

Innovative approaches to improving the quality of philological education

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Abstract: In this article, a new approach to the educational process-innovative methods, the impact of modern methods aimed at improving the quality of interactive activities is discussed.

Key words: innovative education, innovation, interactive methods, pedagogical innovation, question-based educational method.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayoniga qaratilgan yangicha yondashuv-innovatsion metodlar, interfaol harakatlarning o'quv mashg'uloti sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan zamonaviy metodlarning ta'siri haqida mulohaza yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion ta'lim, innovatsiya, interfaol metodlar, pedagogik innovatsiya, savolga asoslangan ta'lim metodi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается новый подход к образовательному процессу – инновационные методы, влияние современных методов, направленных на повышение качества интерактивной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: инновационное образование, инновация, интерактивные методы, педагогическая инновация, вопросный метод обучения.

Modern philology reveals new problems of language and literature study and develops new methods; develops in an integral connection with written sources characteristic of all periods of social life; philological research is conducted with a

deep scientific and critical approach to existing sources. The most important feature of modern philology is to limit its tasks to the tasks of such subjects as history, philosophy, art history, and culture history, which were separated from the bosom of philology, which was once considered a single, integrated science, and at the same time, creative cooperation with them.

M. Behbudi, Fitrat, Cholpon, Avloni, Elbek, Ghozi Olim Yunusov, A. Zahiri, Otajon Hashim, Hodi Zarirov, S. Ibrohimov, P. Shamsiyev, Sh. Khurshid, Olim Sharafiddinov, S. Mutallibov, Izzat Sultan, O. Usmanov, S. Usmanov, U. Tursunov, philology Kamal, V. Abdullayev, V. Zohidov, G'. Karimov, philology Abdullayev, A. Gulomov, H. Sulaymanov, Russian scientists Ye. Polivanov, K. Yudakhin, A. Borovkov, V. Reshetov, A. Kononov, A. Shcherbak, and others have significant contributions. Also Sh. Shoabdurahmanov, G. Abdurahmonov, A. Hayitmetov, A. Kayumov, A. Rustamov, Q. Mahmudov, M. Askarova, H. Rahmatullayev, A. Hajiyev, A. Abdugafurov, B. Valikhojhayev, N. Karimov, T. Mirzayev, B. Nazarov, E. Fozilov, E. Begmatov, H. Ne'matov, A. Nurmonov, N. Makhmudov and others participate in the development of modern Uzbek philology with their scientific research. Currently, pedagogic innovations are widely used in the teaching of philology. Pedagogical innovations are used in order to show positive changes in the relevant field and achieve high-quality results. Interpretation of this type of innovation is reflected in the following steps:

- 1- Birth of a new idea (Discovery stage);
- 2- Grounding of innovation based on a new idea;
- 3- Use of the established innovation in practice;
- 4- Dissemination and wide implementation of the innovation;

5- Dominance of innovation in the relevant field;

6- Alternative.

If the above-mentioned innovative educational stages are used in training sessions, they serve as an important factor in increasing the quality and productivity of education.

The main manifestations of innovation: new ideas, specific goals aimed at changing the system or direction of activity, non-traditional approaches, unusual initiatives, advanced work methods.

Innovative education, in turn, is reflected by the use of innovative methods, that is, interactive methods. One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. It is the responsibility of the teacher to deliver certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, to create skills and competencies in them in relation to certain activities, as well as to control the activities of students, to assess the level of knowledge, skills, and qualifications acquired by them. requires high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process. Pedagogical technology is subjective in nature, that is, every pedagogue should creatively organize the process of education and training based on his ability and professional skills. Pedagogical technologies, regardless of the form, method and means of organization:

- increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activities;
- decision of mutual cooperation between teacher and students;
- ensuring that students acquire thorough knowledge of educational subjects;
- formation of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
- necessary for students to realize their potential

creating conditions;

The "Brainstorming" method ensures the students' activity in the training process, encourages them to think freely and release them from the inertia of the same thinking, collect various ideas on a specific topic, and solve creative tasks. It serves to teach you to overcome the thoughts that appeared at the initial stage of the learning process.

The "Brainstorming" method was recommended by A.F. Osborn, and its main principle and condition is to absolutely prohibit criticism of the ideas expressed by each participant of the training, and to encourage any jokes and jokes. The aim is to ensure the free participation of students in the training process. The effective and successful use of this method in the educational process depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills and breadth of thinking. When using the "brainstorming" method, the number of students should not exceed 15.

Also, one method that challenges the mind to become more intelligent is Inquiry-Based Learning. What if learning is based on questions? That's what inquiry-based learning is all about. In this approach, the teacher guides students to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. To learn these skills, the teacher helps students think through their processes, teaches them possible approaches, and encourages them to try different methods. Students are encouraged to fail as part of the process and then improve their performance in the next activity. Instead of repeating taught answers, students learn to find answers to questions on their own. In this way, students develop strong research skills. In addition, children learn how to choose questions to answer and what questions they can ask. This approach is aimed at students as it requires active participation of students. The teacher guides and teaches, but the students also help to choose the topics of study. This method is considered to

be one of the innovative educational methods and is to attack the mind by asking questions through critical thinking.

List of used literature:

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